

Customer's Behaviour towards Social Media Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Social media has gaining popularity in each and every part of the world. People are nowadays connected to each other with the help of social websites such as Face book, twitter any many more apps available on the internet. So each and every organization is concentrating upon social media and using it as a marketing tool due to its wide reach and economic characteristic. Therefore, Prime objective of this research paper is to measure customer behaviour towards social media marketing and relationship between time devote for respondents and overall effect of social media marketing with the help of 100 respondents as sample size. Percentage analysis and chi square analysis. Social media networks have become as sort of reality in which people communicate, interact and obviously trust.

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INTRODUCTION:

Social media is a term that is used quite alien these days. It is affect that ninety percent of all online users use social media in some way or the other. It is a fact that most of the people will not be able to name more than a handful of social media platforms decides the ounce's that they are using, It may have been due to the pace of development in the social media or just plain lack of interest in the developments that makes it seem like social media jumped out of nowhere and took people by surprise. The emergence of social media begin in the early days of internet when people started sharing information and communicating with each other. Over a period of time as the technology matured. Platforms developed were regular users, without any technological background, could also use the services. Social media marketing also known as online marketing, Internet marketing or e-marketing.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Boyd el at (2008) has summarized reason research social media history the author Berkeley and Michigan state professors. Considered social net works are increasingly attractive for researchers. Fascinated for their usefulness, audience size market research potential. They defines social media are web based media services allow users to built a public or semi-public with in a system, articulated user list with sad relation shared and observed list of relationship of those persons with other people within the system.

Lertdejdech, et.al (2009) studied-demographic, relevance, brand familiarity and behaviour towards social media marketing have significant effects on customer's responses the businesses social media marketing. The questionnaire was used to collect the data from consumers in different demographic groups. Multiple regressions were used to behaviour towards social media marketing. Based on the statically analysis, we provide general guide line for an effective social media marketing.

Bond, et, al. (2010) studied social media brings with it powerful opportunities for engaged with consumers, one method being through interactive marketing. To broaden our understanding and assist in managing marketing communication effectively, this exploratory research investigates their role of social media with in the broader advertising and communications mix. Qualitative focus groups were conducted with consumers to assess perception towards social media marketing.

Sandburg, et.al (2011) studied as today is an era of internet and marketers increased investments in internet. And our researchers studies based on a recent explorative study of 15 years old Swedish teenagers, aim to discuss their exposure-potential, actual and perceived to online marketing with a particularly focus on marketing. They used different methods for their research like Research questions. Our research also indicates sub sequential gender difference in actual exposure of marketing.

WangQingya (2011) studied social media sites continues to grow popularity, it is our premise that technology is a vital part in today’s student equation. The present research investigates customer’s behaviours towards mobile marketing and relationships between attitude and behaviours. An instruments of measuring towards social media marketing. And direct relationship between customer attitudes and customers behaviours. The respondents held negative behaviours receiving social media ads. It may have been because they found social media as irrigating given the personal, intimate nature of mobile phones in social media.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Data required for the survey was collected from various publications, articles, journals and websites. The primary data surveys were conducted through well –structured questionnaire. Data can be collected from different sources and for different reasons. Depend on the content of information, data can be used for various purposes and find most valid and suitable data for the specific research purposes.

SAMPLE SIZE:

The data was collected from 100 respondents using convenience sampling method. First-hand information related to social media marketing. Convenience sampling is a sample taken from a group you has access easily. The idea that anything learned from this study will be applicable to the larger population. By using a large, convenient size, you

are able to more confidently say the sample represents t population.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS:

For purpose of the purpose of analysis the following tools are used: percentage analysis, chi-square analysis and one way Anova test.

OBJECTIVE:

- To study the time devoted by the respondents on social media marketing networking sites
- To study the influence of age and education of customer in selection of social media marketing
- To find out overall effect of social media marketing in forming purchase decisions

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

TABLE –4.1.1 GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

S. No	Gender	No. of respondent	Percentage
1.	Male	70	70
2.	Female	30	30
	Total	100	100

Source: primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table it clear that out of 100 respondents have been taken for the study, 70% of the respondents belongs to female and 30%of the respondents belong to male.

TABLE-4.1.2 AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS

S. No	Age group	No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Below 30	64	64
2.	30-40	35	35
3.	40-50	1	1
4.	Above 50 years	0	0
	Total	100	100

Source data: primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table it clear that out of 100respondents have been taken for the study 64%of the respondents belongs to below 30.35% of the respondents are belong to 30-40.1%of the respondents belong to 40-50.0%of the respondents are above 50years.

TABLE -4.1.3 MARITUS STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

S. No	Maritus status	No.of. respondents	Percentage
1.	Unmarried	40	40
2.	Married	60	60

Source: primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table it clear that out of 100respondents have been taken for the study 64%of the respondents belongs to below 30.35% of the respondents are belong to 30-40.1%of the respondents belong to 40-50.0%of the respondents are above 50years.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS:

The chi-square cure is always positively skived. The man of chi-square distribution equal to the number of degree of freedom. The formula for chi-square test

$$\text{Chi-square} = \sum x = \sum (o-E) 2/E$$

TABLE-4.14AGE GROUPAND EDUCATION QUALIFICATIONS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Age Group	Graduate	Postgraduate	Student	Diploma	Total
Below 20	10	4	0	0	14
20-30	12	15	11	3	41
30-40	3	8	15	0	26
Above 50	5	14	26	3	20
Total	30	41	26	3	100

Source: computed

Ho= There is no significant between Age group and education qualification of social media

TABLE - 4.14(a) CHI- SQUARE TEST

Chi-square value	Table value	Not significant/significant	Null hypothesis
8.998	16.919	Not significant	Accepted

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is clear that the calculate value is lesser than the table value at 5% level of significant. Since there is no significant relationship between age and education qualification. Hence null hypothesis is accepted & alternative hypothesis is rejected.

FINDINGS:

- Majority 70% of the respondents are male.
- Majority 71% of the respondents are of below years of age.
- Majority 52% of the respondents completed Education qualifications.
- There is no significant association between Age group and Education qualifications.

SUGGESTION:

- The social media should engage audiences.
- The social media marketer should delivery consistently.
- Social media should select the best platforms to achieve their goals.
- Social media sites are based on building virtual communities that allow customers to express their wants and needs through online.

CONCLUSION:

In social media marketing is over all 80% of internet users are active in social networks. They spend at least one hour a day average on those social media networks. It concludes that social media networks have become as sort of reality in which people communicate, interact and obviously trust. We also have to be aware that overall 65% of those users' access social networks via mobile device, with strong indicators that is percent will only increase in futures.

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